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Simulated Ground Motion Dataset in the Azores Plateau, Portugal, on Rock and Soil Sites

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ABSTRACT

Building on a previously developed bedrock dataset, this study extends the Azores Plateau ground motion simulations to include soil-amplified records and introduces a comprehensive validation framework. Soil amplification is modeled using one-dimensional soil profiles. A stochastic source-based approach is employed to generate the dataset, incorporating randomization of input-model parameters to account for the aleatory uncertainty in seismic activity. The accuracy of the dataset is verified through a comprehensive validation framework, showing that the randomization effectively captures variance and inter-period correlation observed in records. This work provides a robust dataset for advancing seismic hazard and risk assessment in the Azores Plateau.

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Ground motion simulation; stochastic source-based approach; rock and soil sites; soil amplification; inter-period correlation; Azores (Portugal)

1. Introduction

Nowadays, the potential applications of earthquake ground motions (GMs) in engineering fields are vast. These include deterministic and probabilistic seismic assessment of structural and geotechnical systems (Caicedo et al. 2024; Krinitzsky 1995), development of ground motion models (GMMs) (Karimzadeh, Mohammadi et al. 2023, 2023; Mohammadi et al. 2023), as well as seismic hazard and risk assessment (Bernardo et al. 2022; V. Silva et al. 2015). Thus, large datasets of seismic records, representative of relevant seismic-prone areas worldwide, have been collected. The Next Generation Attenuation (NGA) database, led by the Pacific Earthquake Engineering Research Center (PEER) and subdivided into NGA-West2 (Ancheta et al. 2014), NGA-East (Goulet et al. 2021), and NGA-Sub (Contreras et al. 2022), represents one of the worldwide databases worldwide. Analogously, focused on European regions, there are the Reference Database for Seismic Ground Motion in Europe (RESORCE) (Akkar, Sandikkaya, Şenyurt, et al. 2014), the pan-European Engineering Strong Motion (ESM) (Lanzano et al. 2019), and the Italian Accelerometric Archive (ITACA) (Luzy et al. 2008). Similarly, the strong ground motion database of AFAD-Turkish Accelerometric Database and Analysis Systems (Disaster and Emergency Management Authority 1973) denotes the largest dataset in the Middle East, while the K-NET (Kyoshin network) and KiK-net (Kiban Kyoshin network) networks are both open-source databases encompassing a total of 1742 earthquakes in Japan (Zhu et al. 2021). Nonetheless, one major challenge for the development of robust databases is the lack of recorded accelerograms for large-magnitude events in most regions of interest for seismic hazard

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estimation, which is why the use of GM simulations emerges as a suitable alternative to real records (Caicedo et al. 2023).

GM simulations provide an alternative to full time series of motions for potential scenario events in regions lacking recorded motions. Several simulation frameworks have been developed, including deterministic, stochastic, and hybrid methodologies, each constrained by inherent modeling assumptions (Rezaeian and Sun 2014). Deterministic simulations generally reproduce low-frequency waveforms with higher fidelity but require detailed knowledge of the source and velocity structure. In contrast, stochastic approaches are more widely adopted in engineering seismology owing to their computational efficiency and reduced dependence on complex wave-propagation models (Douglas and Aochi 2008). Nevertheless, their reliability depends on the accurate specification of input-model parameters calibrated to regional seismological data. When properly constrained, stochastic simulation methods provide a robust means of evaluating ground-shaking characteristics and assessing the potential impact of future seismic scenarios (Askan et al. 2015).

Significant efforts have been made to validate GM simulations from both seismological and engineering standpoints (Karimzadeh 2019; Karimzadeh et al. 2019, 2020; Karimzadeh, Hussaini, et al. 2021; Karimzadeh, Kadas, et al. 2021). Zonno et al. (2010) used observations from one near-fault station to validate GM simulations after the 1998 Faial Earthquake in the Azores Islands of Portugal, on bedrock through the stochastic finite-fault method (Motazedian and Atkinson 2005). Burks and Baker (2014) addressed the validation of GM simulations by analyzing response parameters of engineering systems, including the correlation of spectral acceleration across periods (i.e. inter-period correlation), the ratio of maximum-to-median spectral acceleration across all horizontal orientations, and the ratio of inelastic-to-elastic displacement. Bijelić, Lin, and Deierlein (2018) assessed the performance of two tall buildings (20 and 42 stories) under comparable sets of simulated and recorded motions, leading to the identification of bias induced by differences in correlations of spectral values within GM simulations. Bayless and Abrahamson (2018) investigated the impact of the inter-period correlation of GM simulations on structural assessment, pointing out that neglecting this effect could lead to undesired variability, underestimation of dispersion, and nonconservative results in risk assessment. In this regard, Wang et al. (2019) suggested an alternative method to enhance inter-period correlations in simulations through postprocessing techniques. Altindal and Askan (2023) showed that accounting for uncertainty in the primary input-model parameters of scenario-based simulations implicitly generates variability similar to empirical models. These authors observed that their simulations tend to overestimate inter-period correlation compared to Baker and Jayaram (2008) due to the flattened spectral amplitudes of simulated motions when compared to real records. The work by Rezaeian et al. (2024) summarizes recent validation approaches for engineering applications and classified them into various groups that can be used for future validation exercises.

The Azores Plateau is located in the boundary between the North American and Eurasian tectonic plates and is characterized by frequent seismic activity (A. Carvalho et al. 2001). More specifically, the Azores archipelago is composed of nine volcanic islands subdivided into the eastern group, which comprises São Miguel and Santa Maria islands, the central group, which includes Terceira, Graciosa, São Jorge, Pico, and Faial, and the western group, with Flores and Corvo islands. Among them, the eastern group is the most seismically active, with frequent small and occasional large events, followed by the central and western groups, being less prone to seismic activity. Since the 15th century, the group of islands was hit by roughly 33 moderate-to-strong earthquakes. The most recent one was on July 9, 1998, with moment magnitude (M_w) 6.2 on Faial Island, affecting the building stock of the region characterized by stone masonry walls and flexible timber floors (A. Costa and Arêde 2006). These observations raised the interest of researchers in the assessment of seismic damage, post diction, and prediction for future earthquake scenarios (Ferreira, Maio, and Vicente 2017; Guerreiro et al. 2000; Neves et al. 2012). However, as a result of insufficient instrumentation, the region lacks a reliable database of recorded ground motions (Karimzadeh, Mohammadi et al. 2023).

Recently, Karimzadeh and Lourenço (2022), followed by Karimzadeh, Funari, et al. (2023), conducted ground motion simulations for the 1998 Faial earthquake (M_w 6.2). The authors validated the

input-model parameters by comparing them with recorded data and, in a subsequent stage, assessed the seismic response of historic masonry structures using both recorded and simulated datasets. Later, Karimzadeh, Mohammadi et al. (2023) developed a region-specific bedrock ground motion model (GMM for the Azores, utilizing simulated records through a stochastic source-based approach (Assatourians and Atkinson 2012; Motazedian and Atkinson 2005). More recently, Ji et al. (2025) extended this effort by developing a parametric-based GMM utilizing the same bedrock dataset.

The present study builds upon the previously developed bedrock-level simulated dataset for the Azores Plateau and extends it to include soil-amplified records, providing a comprehensive ground motion dataset for both rock and soil sites. Soil amplification is modeled using one-dimensional soil profiles from the region. A robust validation framework is introduced to assess the accuracy of the simulations, focusing on intensity measures, attenuation behavior, residual trends, and inter-period correlation. The accuracy of the simulated dataset is verified through a comprehensive validation process in which the effectiveness of the stochastic sampling of ground motion variability in capturing variance and inter-period correlation of recorded ground motions is demonstrated. The dataset provided is expected to be useful for researchers in the fields of earthquake engineering, seismic hazard and risk assessment. The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides a broad description of the study area. Section 3 presents the results of the simulated GM database, focusing on the methodology, calibration of the model, and relevant statistics of the dataset. The validation of the dataset is addressed in Section 4 by comparing ground motion characteristics that are well constrained by data to predictions from empirical GMMs. Section 5 discusses the limitations of the simulated GM dataset. Finally, relevant conclusions are drawn in Section 6.

2. Study Area

2.1. Tectonic Processes of the Region

The tectonic activity in the Azores plateau is complex, with significant seismic and volcanic activity influenced by the interactions of the North American, Eurasian, and African Plates at the Azores Triple Junction (ATJ). This tectonic setting results in diverse fault systems and significant geological hazards, including earthquakes and volcanic eruptions. This region is characterized by a shallow bathymetry and triangular configuration, likely due to a mantle plume hotspot (Lourenço et al. 1998). Evidence from wave velocities, geochemical data, gravity measurements, and crustal thickness supports the presence of this plume (Silveira et al. 2006). The central and eastern groups of the Azores archipelago are located near the western segment of the Eurasian-African plate boundary (J. Madeira et al. 2015). The Azores Gibraltar Fracture Zone forms part of this boundary, with distinct segments exhibiting unique morphologies and seismotectonic characteristics (J. Madeira et al. 2015). The fracture zone in the Azores is a broad shear zone accommodating different spreading rates north and south of the ATJ and is believed to be moving northward from the eastern fracture zone (Heezen, Tharp, and Ewing 1959; Lourenço et al. 1998; Vogt and Jung 2004).

The central and eastern Azores are within a complex deformation zone with dextral trans-tensile stress, as evidenced by active tectonics and volcanism. The fault pattern consists of two main systems with opposing dips, revealing maximum horizontal tensile stress-oriented northeast-southwest (NE-SW), horizontal compressive stress-oriented northwest-southeast (NW-SE), and vertical intermediate compressive stress. Secondary stress fields in eastern São Miguel and Graciosa islands may alternate with the primary field (Carmo et al. 2015; Hipólito et al. 2013). The island morphology reflects the interaction between volcanic activity, faulting, and denudation processes, affecting formations from the Middle Pleistocene to the Holocene.

Tectonically driven volcanism occurs along faults or at fault intersections, with the region experiencing low- to moderate-size earthquakes mostly at shallow depths (~ 40 km) (Bezzeghoud et al. 2014). The first recorded seismic event in Faial occurred in 1614, when an earthquake hit Terceira Island. Significant earthquakes were documented in the twentieth century, causing considerable

damage in 1924, 1926, 1980, and 1998. The earthquakes of January 1, 1980 (M_w 6.9), and July 9, 1998 (M_w 6.2), were the most recent major events, causing severe damage. The 1998 earthquake had an epicenter offshore, about 10 km NE of Faial Island, with a maximum intensity of VIII near the epicenter. The quake was also felt on Pico and São Jorge islands, with recorded intensities of VII and VI, respectively. The event resulted in nine fatalities, over 150 injuries, and damage to more than 1500 houses. The hardest-hit areas were Riberinha and Espalhafatos, where old stone masonry buildings, particularly vulnerable to seismic activity, sustained heavy damage. A 19th-century bridge also collapsed during the quake (Matias et al. 2007; Senos et al. 1998).

The central and eastern Azores islands (Faial, Pico, São Jorge, Terceira, and Graciosa) each exhibit distinct tectonic features. Active tectonics on the central and eastern Azores islands are plotted in Figure 1. The characteristics of all faults are summarized in Table 1.

Faial Island is 21 km long, 14 km wide, and rises to 1043 m at Cabeço Gordo, featuring two primary fault systems trending west-northwest–east-southeast (WNW-ESE) and north-northwest–south-southeast (NNW-SSE). The WNW-ESE trending Pedro Miguel Graben defines the eastern part of Faial as characterized by normal dextral faults. The southern section includes north-dipping faults such as Rocha Vermelha, Espalamaca, and Flamengos, while the northern section has south-dipping faults like Riberinha and Lomba Grande. South of Caldeira, faults like Lomba do Meio and Lomba de Baixo dip to the northeast, with the Flamengos fault connected to Lomba de Baixo (J. Madeira and Brum da Silveira 2009). The maximum expected magnitude (M_w) from the Espalamaca fault is 6.6 (Wells and Coppersmith 1994).

Graciosa Island, elliptical in shape, is 12 km long and 7 km wide, with a maximum elevation of 402 m at the caldera's southern rim. Its tectonic structure includes NW-SE trending normal faults, cutting through old volcanic complexes of Serra das Fontes and Serra Branca. Key faults are the North and South Serra Branca, South Serra das Fontes, and Saúde-Hortelã. The main north-northeast–south-southwest (NNE-SSW) fault, East Serra das Fontes, is marked by a large southeast-facing scarp (Gaspar et al. 2015; Hipólito et al. 2013).

Figure 1. Active tectonics on the central and eastern Azores islands. The model computational nodes, representative of dummy stations, are shown by triangles.

Table 1. Active faults of the central and eastern Azores islands (Karimzadeh, Mohammadi et al. 2023).

Region	No	Fault Name	Fault Rupture Length		Fault Mechanism	Strike (°)	Dip (°)
			(km)	M_w (max)			
Faial	F1	Ribeirinha	12.5	6.3	Normal	115	75
Faial	F2-E	Lomba Grande Eastern segment	12.5	6.3	Normal	115	80
Faial	F2-W	Lomba Grande Western segment	12.5	6.3	Normal	115	80
Faial	F3	Rocha Vermelha	14	6.4	Normal	290	55
Faial	F4	Espalamaca	20.3	6.6	Normal	295	70
Faial	F5	Flamengos	11.5	6.3	Normal	290	70
Faial	F6	Lomba do Meio	4	5.2	Normal	295	70
Faial	F7	Lomba de Baixo	4	5.2	Normal	300	50
Faial	F8	Capelo	8.8	5.8	Normal	290	90
Graciosa	G1	Saúde-Hortelã	5	5.9	Normal	140	–
Graciosa	G2	South Serra das Fontes	4.6	5.8	Normal	126	–
Graciosa	G3	North Serra Branca	4.8	5.9	Normal	302	–
Graciosa	G4	South Serra Branca	3.2	5.7	Normal	305	–
Graciosa	G5	East Serra das Fontes	4.6	5.8	Normal	340	–
Pico	P1	Lagoa do Capitão	8.8	6.2	Normal	120	80–90
Pico	P2	Topo	7.5	6.1	Normal	285	70–90
Pico	P3	Cabeço do Sintrão	21	6.6	Normal	293	–
São Jorge	SJ1	Picos	33	6.8	Normal	120	90
São Jorge	SJ2	Pico Carvão	12	6.3	Normal	285	75–90
São Jorge	SJ3	Urze-São João	15	6.4	Normal	304	80
São Jorge	SJ4	Cume Faja do Belo	7.4	6.1	Normal	120	70
São Jorge	SJ5	Serra do Topo	7.2	6.1	Normal	140	–
São Jorge	SJ6	Ribeira Seca	7.3	6.1	Normal	160–170	–
Terceira	T1	Lajes	8.2	6.1	Normal	138	70–90
Terceira	T2	Fontinhas	9	6.2	Normal	313	–
Terceira	T3	Cruz do Marco	5	5.9	Normal	310	70
Terceira	T4	Santa Bárbara	12.9	6.4	Normal	308	70

According to J. Madeira et al. (2015), the maximum expected magnitudes range between M_w 5.7 and 5.9, estimated using the empirical fault-rupture length relationships proposed by Wells and Coppersmith (1994).

Pico Island, with dimensions of 46 km in length and up to 15.8 km in width, has an altitude of 2351 m at Montanha do Pico. Its tectonic structure resembles that of Faial Island, featuring two major fault systems: a WNW-ESE trending system with normal dextral Lagoa do Capitão and Topo fault zones forming the Brejos Graben, overlain by Pico volcano in the west, and a NNW–SSE trending system with less frequent conjugate faults, such as the Cabeço do Sintrão fault (J. Madeira and Brum da Silveira 2009). The island's maximum expected M_w ranges from 6.1 to 6.6, with normal faulting mechanisms (J. Madeira et al. 2015; Wells and Coppersmith 1994).

São Jorge Island, 54 km long and 7 km wide, rising to 1053 m at Pico da Esperança, has tectonic features similar to Faial and Pico Islands, including a normal dextral WNW-ESE fault system and a normal left-lateral NNW-SSE fault system. The western half is dominated by Picos and Pico do Carvão fault zones, while the eastern region features significant WNW-ESE trending faults like Urze-São João and Cume Faja do Belo. Major NNW-SSE faults include Ribeira Seca and Serra de Topo. Expected magnitudes range from M_w 6.1 to 6.8 for these faults (J. Madeira and Brum da Silveira 2009). Maximum expected magnitudes range from M_w 6.1 to 6.8 for these faults, all exhibiting normal fault mechanisms (Madeira and Brum da Silveira 2009; Wells and Coppersmith 1994).

Terceira Island, elliptical and 30 km long along its major axis, rises to 1021 m at Santa Barbara. It has experienced significant earthquakes in 1614, 1841, and 1980. The primary tectonic features are NW-SE trending faults, with Lajes Graben traversing the older NE region. Key faults include the NE-dipping Fontinhas and Cruz do Marco faults and the SW-dipping Lajes Fault. The Santa Bárbara Graben spans the Santa Bárbara volcano (Hirn et al. 1980; M. Silva 2005). The maximum anticipated magnitudes range from M_w 5.9 to 6.4 (J. Madeira et al. 2015; Wells and Coppersmith 1994).

2.2. Soil Structure of the Region

All the islands of the Azores Archipelago have a volcanic origin, and the land is composed of rocks and deposits of volcanic nature. In these islands, all geological formations are very heterogeneous, and it is usual to find a set of harder formations with intercalations of softer layers corresponding to different eruption episodes (Teves-Costa and Veludo 2013). Some islands are mostly formed by basaltic rocks and pyroclastic materials of both basaltic composition (Pico, S. Jorge, and Santa Maria Islands) and trachytic composition (cinders, ashes, pumices, tuffs) (S. Miguel, Terceira, Graciosa, Faial, Flores, and Corvo islands) (M. Madeira et al. 2007). However, as pointed out in (Teves-Costa, Carvalho, and Rodrigues, 2014), the volcanic origin of the geological formations produces large variability of these profiles (similar soil profile but with different layer thickness due to the occurrence of several volcanic episodes with different types and different magnitudes with varying durations of time).

As illustrated in Figure 2, the Portuguese national annex of Eurocode 8 (IPQ 2010) presents five geologic profiles for the Azores region (type I to V) with shear wave velocities for the volcanic materials observed. These profiles are specifically for the Azores islands, as they do not fit the considered set of profiles defined in Eurocode 8 (Malheiro 2007). Still, the specific soil profiles were associated with soil types A to C of Eurocode 8 (European Committee for Standardization 2005), with profile I classified as soil type A, profiles II to IV as soil type B, and profile V as soil type C.

According to Malheiro (2007), Terceira Island mainly features soil profile types II to IV, while S. Miguel Island includes soil profile types I, II, IV, and V. In contrast, São Jorge Island primarily exhibits soil profile types I and V. From 2012 to 2015, within the scope of the national project SiGMA (strong ground motion for the Azores), ambient vibration measurements performed in array and the multichannel analysis of surface waves (MASW) method were conducted at several sites located on the Terceira, Pico, Faial, and São Jorge islands. The results allowed the identification of profile types I, II, II/III, III, and V on Terceira Island, mostly profile types III and one type II/III in Faial, and profile type III in São Jorge and Pico (Teves-Costa, Carvalho, and Madeira 2014). These authors proposed, as well, values for average shear wave velocity of the top 30 m (V_{S30}), namely $V_{S30} > 700$ m/s for profile type I, $360 < V_{S30} < 700$ m/s for soil profile type II, $360 < V_{S30} < 580$ m/s for profile type III, and $230 < V_{S30} < 260$ m/s for soil profile type V. These authors recognize the overlapping of V_{S30} values, but they defined profile classes taking into consideration the difference of other parameters (Teves-Costa and Veludo 2013), namely peak frequency of the transfer function and amplification factor of the peak ground acceleration for several inputs. No profile of type IV was found in the central group of Azores. At the same time, within the scope of the same project, Malfeito (2015) and Malfeito, Carvalho, and Bilé Serra (2014) developed and applied an expedited methodology that allowed the simulation of synthetic soil profiles for the Azores, considering the variance in layer thickness and material properties. For each profile and each layer, the aleatory uncertainty of thickness, volumetric mass, shear wave velocity, and plasticity index was modeled by a uniform distribution. About 200 synthetic soil profiles were built for each type of soil preconized in the national annex of Eurocode 8 (Figure 2), and an average of V_{S30} was determined for each set of profiles of each soil type (Malfeito et al. 2014) namely, $V_{S30} = 722$ m/s for soil type I, $V_{S30} = 560$ m/s for soil type II, $V_{S30} = 340$ m/s for soil type III, $V_{S30} = 370$ m/s for soil type IV and $V_{S30} = 360$ m/s for soil type V.

3. Simulated Ground Motion Database

3.1. Ground Motion Simulation Methodology

The stochastic approaches, originating with the point-source method proposed by Boore (1983), feature the following shear wave acceleration spectrum at an observation point:

$$A(f) = CM_0 [(2\pi f)^2 / (1 + (f/f_c)^2)] G(R) e^{(-\pi f R / Q(f)\beta)} e^{(-\pi f t_0)} S(f) \quad (1)$$

Figure 2. Stratigraphic profiles at Azores Island, after Malheiro (Malheiro 2007) (adapted from (Miranda et al. 2018)).

where C is a scaling constant that encompasses factors such as the radiation pattern for shear waves, free surface amplification, division of horizontal components, crustal density, and shear wave velocity (β). M_0 denotes the seismic moment in Nm. The term within the squared brackets corresponds to an ω^{-2} source spectrum, as introduced by Brune (1970) while f_c represents the corner frequency in Hz. $G(R)$ represents geometrical spreading, which accounts for distance (R)-dependent attenuation, while $Q(f)$ denotes the quality factor, accounting for frequency (f)-dependent anelastic attenuation. k_0 denotes zero-distance kappa for upper crust attenuation, and $S(f)$ represents the frequency (f)-dependent soil amplification factor.

The initial point-source method evolved with the introduction of the finite-fault approach (Beresnev and Atkinson 1998; Boore 2003; Motazedian and Atkinson 2005). Boore (2009) later refined the methodology proposed by Motazedian and Atkinson (2005), incorporating enhancements such as scaling high-frequency motions using the integral of the squared acceleration spectrum instead of the squared velocity spectrum. Furthermore, improvements included eliminating the truncation of sub-fault time series. In this updated version, the duration of sub-fault motions is now determined by the reciprocal of the corner frequency linked to each sub-fault.

The present study utilizes the EXSIM12 platform, applying the latest version of the stochastic finite-fault ground motion simulation approach to generate acceleration time series of scenario earthquakes (Assatourians and Atkinson 2012). The methodology, originally based on the FINSIM code developed by Beresnev and Atkinson (1998), has been enhanced through the improvements proposed by Boore (2009). The enhanced version of this approach improves the low-frequency component of the simulations. By considering factors such as earthquake magnitude, fault geometry, strike, dip, slip distribution, density, and rupture velocity, the method simulates the fault rupture. The seismic signal at any observation site is obtained by integrating the point-source response in terms of the source contribution with attenuation parameters and site effects in the time domain (Boore 1983). Therefore, the ruptured fault plane is represented as a grid of smaller sub-sources, each modeled as a point-source with an ω^{-2} source spectrum, as proposed by Boore (1983). Each sub-source ruptures with an appropriate time delay, determined by its distance from the hypocenter. The contributions from these delayed sub-sources are then summed in the time domain, as follows:

$$A(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N H_i Y_i(t + \Delta t_i + T_i) \quad (2)$$

where $A(t)$ resembles the total seismic signal at time t , N corresponds to the total number of sub-sources, Y_i is the seismic signal of the i^{th} sub-source obtained from inverse Fourier transform, Δt_i represents the combined delay due to fracture initiation and the distance of the i^{th} sub-source from the hypocenter, T_i accounts for additional randomization related to a fraction of rise time and finally, the term H_i is the normalization factor for the i^{th} sub-source, ensuring energy conservation, defined by Eq. 3:

$$H_i = \frac{M_0}{M_{0i}} \sqrt{\frac{\sum_j \left(\frac{f_0^2 f_j^2}{f_0^2 + f_j^2} \right)^2}{N \sum_j \left(\frac{f_{0i}^2 f_j^2}{f_{0i}^2 + f_j^2} \right)^2}} \quad (3)$$

where f_0 denotes the corner frequency of the primary fault plane, f_j represents the frequency ordinate of the j^{th} component, M_0 is the overall seismic moment, and M_{0i} and f_{0i} refer to the seismic moment and corner frequency of the i^{th} sub-source, respectively. These parameters are calculated as follows:

$$M_{0i} = \frac{M_0 \times S_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N S_i} \quad (4)$$

$$f_{0i} = 4.9 \times 10^6 \beta_s \left(\frac{\Delta\sigma}{p \times M_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \text{ where } p = \begin{cases} \frac{N_R}{N} & \text{if } N_R < N \times PP \\ PP & \text{if } N_R \geq N \times PP \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where S_i represents the slip of the i^{th} sub-source in Eq. (4). In Eq. (5), N_R is the total number of sub-sources that become active when the i^{th} sub-source is triggered, $\Delta\sigma$ denotes the stress drop in bars, and PP is the pulsing percentage. The algorithm employs a dynamic corner frequency approach. In this method, the corner frequencies of the active sub-sources decrease as the rupture progresses until they reach a specific level defined by PP . For the remaining sub-sources, their respective corner frequencies remain constant.

3.2. Calibration of the Input-Model Parameters in Terms of Source, Path, and Site Effects

This section first summarizes the former studies by Karimzadeh, Mohammadi et al. (2023) followed by Ji et al. (2025), which generated the bedrock-only simulated dataset forming the basis of the current work, and then introduces the current study focusing on soil amplification. Previous research by Karimzadeh, Mohammadi et al. (2023) used the EXSIM12 platform (Assatourians and Atkinson 2012) to extensively simulate acceleration time series for 23 scenario events in bedrock.

The study by J. Madeira et al. (2015) estimates a maximum expected M_w 6.8 earthquake for the region based on fault length. The simulations by Karimzadeh, Mohammadi et al. (2023) involved modeling events with magnitudes (M_w) ranging from 5.0 to 6.8 in 0.1 magnitude increments, each corresponding to ruptures of different active faults within the region. Specifically, the simulations considered ten fault ruptures: nine on Faial Island (F1, F2E, F2W, F3, F4, F5, F6, F7, F8, detailed in Table 1) and only one on São Jorge Island (SJ1, detailed in Table 1). These faults were selected due to their representative seismological characteristics, including maximum magnitude, orientation, and fault structure. Additionally, they encompass a range of fault properties observed on other islands, making them a robust choice for the simulations.

The simulations spanned various active faults on the Azores Plateau, incorporating aleatory uncertainty specific to the region within the established framework. The simulations were executed across 359 nodes (see Figure 1) on all islands, with a grid size of 1 km, and were performed for bedrock conditions. Region-specific input-model parameters provided by Karimzadeh and Lourenço (2022) and Karimzadeh, Funari, et al. (2023), were used for calibration, based on validations against four

observed motions from the 1998 Faial earthquake (M_w 6.2). Key parameters such as hypocenter location, stress drop, pulsing percentage, quality factor, and kappa (Boore 2009; Motazedian and Atkinson 2005) were treated as random variables to account for uncertainty in source and attenuation effects. Regional models with probability distribution functions (PDFs) and their ranges were derived from A. Carvalho, Reis, and Vales (2016). Shear wave velocities were estimated considering the depth of the earthquake and 1.75 as the ratio between the P-wave velocity and the S-wave velocity, as in A. Carvalho, Reis, and Vales (2016) and Karimzadeh, Mohammadi et al. (2023). These values are consistent with the one-dimensional (1D) velocity models employed by the Instituto Português do Mar e da Atmosfera (IPMA) (Custódio et al. 2015), which are constrained by regional seismic data. Any given event was subjected to 30 Monte Carlo simulations, each using different combinations of input-model parameters. Consequently, each scenario event was simulated with 30 unique sets of random input-model parameters, resulting in a total of 690 simulations across 359 sites. Therefore, the simulations for bedrock generated a total of 247,710 acceleration time series. Table 2 summarizes the input-model parameters used for the bedrock simulations conducted by Karimzadeh, Mohammadi et al. (2023) This dataset was subsequently utilized by Ji et al. (2025) to develop a parametric-based GMM.

The stochastic simulations account for aleatory variability by randomly sampling key input-model parameters, namely, hypocenter location, pulsing percentage, stress drop, kappa, and quality factor (Q), within physically constrained ranges (listed in Table 2) obtained from regional calibration studies (A. Carvalho, Reis, and Vales 2016).

Figure 3 illustrates the random sampling of each parameter, consistent with the descriptions provided in Table 2. As in Atkinson and Boore (2006), the effects of aleatory uncertainty are considered by expressing random variability in the parameter from one ground motion realization to another.

Building upon the bedrock dataset, the present work extends the simulations to soil sites using one-dimensional stochastic nonlinear site response analysis. Within this context, the response spectrum at 5% damping ratio at the bedrock of each one of the 359 grid points is calculated, using the stochastically generated dataset of ground motions described previously, and transformed into a power spectral density function (Hussaini et al. 2025; Lutes and Sarkani 2004), $S_o(\omega)$, using the

Table 2. Input-model parameters of simulations (Karimzadeh, Mohammadi et al. 2023).

Parameter	Value
Crustal Thickness, D (km)	13
Crustal Density (g/cm^3)	Depth = 0.0km \rightarrow 2.67 Depth = 2.5km \rightarrow 2.77 Depth = 8.0km \rightarrow 2.86 Depth = 14.0km \rightarrow 2.93
Shear Wave Velocity (km/s)	Depth = 0.0km \rightarrow 3.1 Depth = 2.5km \rightarrow 3.7 Depth = 8.0km \rightarrow 4.2 Depth = 14.0km \rightarrow 4.6
Rupture Velocity/Shear Wave Velocity	0.8
Geometric Spreading	$R^{-1.0}$ $R \leq 1.5D$ km $R^{0.0}$ $1.5D$ km $< R \leq 2.5D$ km $R^{-0.5}$ $R > 2.5D$ km
Duration Model (R in km)	$T_0 + 0.1R$
Window Type	Saragoni-Hart
Damping	5%
Slip Weight	Random
Iseed	309
Hypocenter Location	Uniform distribution: along the length and width
Pulsing Percent	Uniform distribution: 30–50
Kappa (seconds)	Uniform distribution: 0.075 ± 0.02
Stress Drop (bars)	Lognormal distribution: 110 ± 20
Quality Factor	Lognormal distribution: $(76 \pm 11)r^{0.69 \pm 0.09}$

Figure 3. Aleatory variability through parameter randomization. "Density" = power spectral density.

classical theory of a stationary random process. For each node, site effects are then evaluated following an equivalent stochastic nonlinear one-dimensional ground response analysis (A. Carvalho et al. 2008; Serra and Caldeira 2020) applied to the 200 stratified soil profile units of each soil type of Eurocode 8 (European Committee for Standardization 2005). In this methodology, soil non-linearity is modeled by iteratively adjusting the stiffness and damping properties as functions of the average shear strain in each soil level (Serra and Caldeira 2020). This approach has been implemented to assess soil effects in the Lisbon metropolitan area, with further details provided in A. Carvalho et al. (2008) and A. C. Costa et al. (2010). It is noted that the randomized input parameters are physics-based and regionally constrained, derived from A. Carvalho, Reis, and Vales (2016) and subsequent calibration studies, ensuring that each Monte Carlo realization remains consistent with the regional seismotectonic context.

In brief, the procedure involves defining, for each soil layer, properties such as density, low-strain shear modulus, and the shear-strain-dependent secant shear modulus reduction and damping ratio curves. The iterative process to ensure that the shear modulus, G , and damping ratio, ξ , are consistent with the computed shear strains is as follows (A. C. Costa et al. 2010; Kramer 1996):

- (i) Assign initial values of G and ξ based on shear wave velocity, density, and plasticity index;
- (ii) Compute the ground response using the initial G and ξ ;
- (iii) Determine the maximum shear strain using the classical stationary random process theory;
- (iv) Select new equivalent linear values of G and ξ corresponding to the estimated shear strain;
- (v) Repeat steps ii–iv until the differences in G and ξ between successive iterations fall below a specified tolerance in all layers.

Once convergence is attained, the transfer function, $H_a(\omega)$, of each soil profile is obtained, representing the ratio between the outcrop acceleration and the absolute acceleration at the surface of the 1D vertically propagating shear wave column of the stratified soil medium. The transfer function $H_a(\omega)$ of each soil unit is calculated, i.e. the transfer function between outcrop acceleration and the absolute acceleration at the top of the 1D vertically propagating shear wave column of the stratified soil

Figure 4. Example of a soil profile type III. Left: mass density, middle: shear wave velocity, right: plasticity index (Malfeito 2015; Malfeito, Carvalho, and Bilé Serra 2014).

medium. The power spectral density function of acceleration (Hussaini et al. 2025; Lutes and Sarkani 2004), $S_a(\omega)$, at the surface, is then obtained as:

$$S_a(\omega) = S_o(\omega)|H_a(\omega)|^2 \quad (6)$$

The $H_a(\omega)$ of the profile type considered is the median of the 200 transfer functions obtained at each node.

As remarked in Section 2, the main profile type for the Azores region is profile type III, according to the work by Teves-Costa and Veludo (2013). Therefore, this paper considers soil amplification corresponding to soil type III, and Figure 4 illustrates one soil type III example out of 200.

3.3. Statistics of the Simulated Dataset

Figure 5 presents general statistics regarding M_w and Joyner-Boore distances (R_{JB}) of the dataset. These statistics are independent of the shear wave velocity since the reference bedrock ($V_{S30} = 4000 \text{ m/s}$) and soil profile III ($V_{S30} = 340 \text{ m/s}$) datasets differ simply due to the soil amplification, with the former representing an idealized no-amplification condition. Within the range of M_w 5.0 to 6.8, there is a uniform distribution with around 10,000 records at each bin defined by increments of 0.1 in M_w , with two peaks of approximately 20,000 and 40,000 records at M_w values of 5.2 and 6.3, respectively. The peaks are attributed to different faults capable of reproducing scenarios with similar maximum magnitude. Likewise, the R_{JB} histogram indicates predominantly near-fault records, with the maximum value of 50,000 occurring in the 0–10 km range, gradually reducing up to 100 km. A second local peak of approximately 35,000 records is observed at R_{JB} distances over 120 km. This is attributed to the distribution of the selected nodes employed for simulations. The scatter plot in Figure 5c further demonstrates the M_w and R_{JB} distributions of simulated data, showing an approximately consistent distribution of the ground motion simulations in the range of 10 to 100 km for each M_w bin.

Figures 6 and 7 show the distribution of peak ground acceleration (PGA) and peak ground velocity (PGV) with respect to the distance metric R_{JB} , independently for bedrock and soil profile III type, respectively. PGA and PGV denote the most representative and widely known

Figure 5. General statistics of the dataset in terms of (a) histogram of moment magnitude (M_w), (b) histogram of Joyner and Boore distance (R_{JB}), and (c) distribution of M_w with respect to R_{JB} .

intensity measures (IMs) within the dataset. As expected, higher values of PGA and PGV are observed for lower R_{JB} and higher values of M_w , which is clear thanks to the color scale for M_w . This behavior is consistent with observations in GMMs (Karimzadeh, Mohammadi et al. 2023, 2023; Mohammadi et al. 2023) and will be further studied in Section 4 for the validation of the dataset. Moreover, the amplification effect is clear when comparing Figures 6 and 7, since both metrics PGA and PGV exhibit larger values for the case of soil profile III. Wavelet analysis was conducted based on Baker (2007) for the quantitative classification of pulse-like records, revealing 1579 pulse-like motions in bedrock and 1620 for soil profile III, out of 247,710 simulations for each soil type. In each case, the ratio of pulse-like motions is less than 1%, which is lower than expected from empirical observations (Chen, Liu, and Beer 2022; Kohrangi, Vamvatsikos, and Bazzurro 2019). This feature will be deeply analyzed in Section 4. Finally, Figure 8 presents the normalized 5% damped spectral acceleration (SA) for bedrock and soil profile III; SA values are normalized by their respective PGA values. The figure also includes the 50th, 16th, and 84th fractile of SA/PGA, illustrating the confidence interval corresponding to one standard deviation (σ).

Figure 6. Peak ground acceleration (PGA) and peak ground velocity (PGV) distributions with respect to the distance metric R_{JB} for bedrock.

Figure 7. Peak ground acceleration (PGA) and peak ground velocity (PGV) distributions with respect to the distance metric R_{JB} for soil profile III.

(a) Bedrock

(b) Soil profile III

Figure 8. Normalized 5% damped spectral acceleration (SA) normalized by peak ground acceleration (PGA) as a function of period (T) for the Azores dataset.

4. Validation of the Simulated Database

The input-model parameters adopted in this study, covering tectonic information, geometric and anelastic attenuation models, rupture velocity, and other source and path characteristics, were originally developed for the Azores region based on the Azores ground motion dataset compiled by A. Carvalho, Reis, and Vales (2016). That study derived source and attenuation parameters from past seismic events recorded across the Azores Plateau using data from the Portuguese digital seismic and accelerometric network. These parameters were subsequently validated for the 1998 Faial earthquake (M_w 6.2) in Karimzadeh and Lourenço (2022) and further confirmed in Karimzadeh, Funari, et al. (2023, 2023). In those studies, several alternative parameter sets were tested to optimize the agreement between simulated and recorded motions from the 1998 event. Among them, set 2 produced the most favorable results, achieving the highest goodness-of-fit (GOF) scores according to the method of Olsen and Mayhew (2010). Very good GOF values were reported for the majority of stations that recorded the Faial earthquake. Table 3 summarizes the GOF scores computed in Karimzadeh and Lourenço (2022) and Karimzadeh, Mohammadi, et al. (2023) for the four available strong-motion stations. In these validation studies, a broad set of intensity measures was used to calculate GOF scores, including PGA, PGV, peak ground displacement, PGV/PGA, Arias intensity, cumulative absolute velocity, acceleration spectrum intensity, modified acceleration spectrum intensity for 0.1–2.5 s (Yakut and Yilmaz 2008), velocity spectrum intensity, Housner intensity, bracketed duration, Fourier amplitude spectra (0.1–25 Hz), and SA (0–4 s, 5% damping). The consistently high GOF values across these metrics confirm that the adopted input-model parameters reliably represent the region-specific source, path, and site characteristics. Furthermore, as demonstrated by Karimzadeh, Funari, et al. (2023), these validated parameters also produced accurate simulations of the seismic response of prototype masonry structures and successfully replicated the observed damage to a historical church affected by the 1998 Faial event.

When it comes to scenario simulations, it is essential to subject the simulated dataset to a rigorous validation framework before applying it in engineering practice. Due to the lack of well-documented strong ground motion records in the Azores region, direct time series comparisons are not feasible. Therefore, validation is made by demonstrating that the simulations capture ground motion characteristics within the empirical data range and reliably extrapolate these characteristics for unobserved earthquake scenarios (Rezaeian et al. 2024). First, a schematic comparison is performed between the simulated dataset and results from various GMMs. This comparison assesses whether the simulated dataset aligns with existing empirically developed GMMs in terms of attenuation patterns, intensity levels, and variability. Such comparative analysis is common in both engineering and seismology (Rezaeian et al. 2024). Next, the variability and inter-period correlation of normalized residual of spectral ordinates are investigated.

Given the absence of a region-specific empirical GMM and recorded strong ground motions for the Azores region, six GMMs were selected for the analysis. These include: one GMM developed specifically for volcanic regions (Atkinson 2010), two GMMs based on pan-European datasets (Akkar, Sandikkaya, and Bommer 2014; Kotha et al. 2020), a GMM tailored to regions with moderate seismicity (Bindi et al. 2017), a regional GMM developed for Türkiye (Akkar and Cagnan 2010), and the GMM proposed by Boore, Joyner, and Fumal (1997), which was identified by Oliveira, Sigbjörnsson, and Ólafsson (2004) as potentially suitable for the Azores region. For brevity, acronyms

Table 3. Goodness-of-fit (GOF) scores for the real and simulated records of the 1998 Faial earthquake (M_w 6.2) (Karimzadeh, Funari, et al. 2023).

Station Code	Region	Latitude (°)	Longitude (°)	Epicentral distance, R_{epi} (km)	GOF	Fit Type
GZC	Graciosa	39.084	−28.006	72	68	Very good
PVI	Pico	38.726	−27.057	132	67	Very good
HOR	Horta	38.530	−28.630	11	72	Very good
SEB	Santa Cruz das Flores	38.668	−27.088	129	57	Fair

are assigned to each GMM in this study: A10 (Atkinson 2010), ASB14 (Akkar, Sandikkaya, and Bommer 2014), KWBC20 (Kotha et al. 2020), BCKBSG17 (Bindi et al. 2017), AC10 (Akkar and Cagnan 2010), and BJF1997 (Boore, Joyner, and Fumal 1997).

Figures 9–12 illustrate the attenuation characteristics of the simulated datasets compared to the selected GMMs, focusing on PGA, PGV, and SA with 5% damping ratio at periods of 0.5 s and 1.0 s for M_w of 5.5 and 6.5, respectively. The figures show the mean and one-standard-deviation range of the selected GMMs, enabling a visual comparison with the simulated dataset. The GMMs exhibit varying attenuation behaviors due to being developed based on different ground motion datasets from different regions. Nevertheless, the simulated dataset, tailored specifically to the Azores region, shows a generally consistent attenuation behavior.

When considering the soft soil effect (i.e. soil profile III with $V_{S30} = 340$ m/s), the selected GMMs generally show higher intensity amplification compared to the simulations relative to their bedrock counterparts. This discrepancy may stem from regional differences in site amplifications between the GMMs and simulations. Additionally, the simulations in this study rely on 1-D site response assumptions, whereas GMMs may implicitly account for more complex 3-D amplification effects. Future studies could improve the accuracy of simulations by incorporating 3-D site amplification effects. Despite these differences, the simulated results largely fall within one standard deviation of most GMMs.

For PGA on bedrock, the simulations generally align with BCKBSG17, A10, AC10, and BJF1997, with attenuation occurring more rapidly than in BJF1997. For the soil profile III dataset, the simulations align closely with the GMMs for M_w of 5.5 but show lower intensity levels at M_w of 6.5 compared to the GMMs. For PGV, simulations on bedrock closely match ASB14, regardless of M_w , while on soil profile III, they align with all GMMs. The differences in behavior for GMMs on bedrock may stem from regional variations in site amplification effects, as GMMs incorporate diverse geological settings.

Figure 9. Attenuation of simulated ground motions compared to empirical GMMs in terms of PGA for M_w of 5.5 and 6.5, for bedrock and soil profile III conditions.

Figure 10. Attenuation of simulated ground motions compared to empirical GMMs in terms of PGV for M_w of 5.5 and 6.5, for bedrock and soil profile III conditions.

Figure 11. Attenuation of simulated ground motions compared to empirical GMMs in terms of SA at the period of 0.5 s for M_w of 5.5 and 6.5, for bedrock and soil profile III conditions.

Figure 12. Attenuation of simulated ground motions compared to empirical GMMs in terms of SA at the period of 1.0 s for M_w of 5.5 and 6.5, for bedrock and soil profile III conditions.

Additionally, while the simulations use a theoretically high V_{S30} value to represent bedrock, the GMMs may define bedrock using different V_{S30} limits, which can introduce regional site effects into the comparison. A similar trend is observed for SA at 0.5 s and 1.0 s, where the bedrock simulations produce higher intensity levels than most GMMs, except for KWBC20, where the simulations are lower. However, the soil profile III simulations show better alignment with the GMMs. Finally, the different amplitudes and decay rates with respect to other GMMs are mainly due to the complex seismic wave propagation and heterogeneities in the volcanic environment of the Azores islands studied.

To further evaluate the simulations in terms of geometric and anelastic attenuation, **Figure 13** compares the mean SA of the simulations for M_w 5.5 and 6.5 on bedrock across three R_{JB} ranges: 0–10 km, 45–55 km, and 90–110 km. As R_{JB} increases, a decrease in SA intensity is expected due to the

Figure 13. Variation of mean SA across different R_{JB} ranges (0–10 km, 45–55 km, and 90–110 km) for M_w of 5.5 and 6.5 on bedrock.

dissipation of seismic energy through geometric and anelastic attenuation (Boore 2003). The high-frequency content of ground motions generally attenuates more rapidly, causing the peak SA value to shift toward longer periods as the source-to-site distance (i.e. R_{JB}) increases, as demonstrated in Figure 13. The same conclusions are valid for higher magnitudes, at the same distance.

The soil amplification behavior is nonlinear in relation to the intensity of bedrock motion. For stronger ground motions, the soil nonlinear behavior begins to have a stronger influence and dominates the variability on site response (Regnier et al. 2013). When the ground motion exceeds a certain threshold, site response changes occur, reflecting a shift of the resonant frequencies toward lower values and a reduction in the associated amplification (Ren et al. 2017).

Figure 14 illustrates soil amplification as a function of vibration periods for M_w of 5.5 and 6.5, with the color bar indicating the range of R_{JB} values. This region-specific soil behavior suggests that stronger ground motions (M_w 6.5) induce nonlinear soil softening, which shifts peak amplification toward longer periods (especially for shorter distances) and attenuates high-frequency content (Ren et al., 2017). The same trend can be inferred from Figure 15. The limited variation in the peak period between the M_w 5.5 and M_w 6.5 scenarios at larger distances ($R_{JB} > 30$ km) primarily results from the lower input motion levels, under which the soil response remains essentially linear. Conversely, at short distances ($R_{JB} < 10$ km), the stronger shaking induced by the M_w 6.5 event triggers nonlinear soil behavior. It is important to emphasize that the current study examines only a soil profile III representative of the Azores region. Given the high heterogeneity of volcanic soils, as highlighted by (Wesley 2003), it is unrealistic to expect a single soil profile to capture all possible site-response

Figure 14. Soil amplification as a function of vibration period across R_{JB} for M_w of 5.5 and 6.5.

Figure 15. Variation of mean SA across different R_{JB} ranges (0–10 km, 45–55 km, and 90–110 km) for M_w of 5.5 and 6.5 on soil profile III.

behaviors. This underscores the importance of future investigations into the variability of volcanic soils and its influence on seismic site effects, which is beyond the scope of the present analysis.

An important indicator in the validation process of simulated ground motions is the inter-period correlation of normalized residuals of spectral acceleration (ε) with respect to an empirical GMM. This is important for the seismic demand assessment of multi-degree-of-freedom structures, which can be excited at various vibrational periods (Burks and Baker 2014). The ε value can be calculated using Baker (2011):

$$\varepsilon(T) = \frac{\ln SA(T) - \mu_{\ln SA}(M_w, R_{JB}, V_{S30}, T)}{\sigma_{\ln SA}(T)} \quad (7)$$

where $\mu_{\ln SA}(M_w, R_{JB}, V_{S30}, T)$ and $\sigma_{\ln SA}(T)$ are the mean value and standard deviation of $\ln SA(T)$ estimated from the GMM, respectively. $\ln SA(T)$ is the natural logarithm of simulated SA values, which are considered within the period range of 0.1 to 2.0 s. The ε values are calculated for all simulations in the dataset, encompassing all magnitudes and distances. The correlation between ε values at different periods, indicated by ρ_ε , is calculated using the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient. Therefore, the inter-period correlations are derived from the full set of simulations. Figures 16 and 17 illustrate ρ_ε for the bedrock and soil profile III datasets, respectively. Recorded ground motions typically exhibit strong correlations between spectral ordinates at neighboring periods (Baker 2011). Therefore, high ρ_ε values at neighboring periods indicate that the simulations capture the inherent period-to-period relationships, as reflected in the reference GMM, even if there is a systematic over- or under-estimation of spectral ordinates across these periods. In contrast, low to near-zero ρ_ε values suggest that the residuals behave randomly, meaning the simulation fails to capture the physical coupling observed in recorded data. The figures show that ρ_ε values calculated based on BJF1997 are higher across the considered period range compared to the other GMMs in both datasets. The differences in ρ_ε are attributed to the different ground motion datasets and their inherent variability used in the development of each GMM. Nonetheless, the observed patterns in ρ_ε remain largely consistent across all selected GMMs.

While these comparisons demonstrate consistency in inter-period correlation patterns across the selected GMMs, they do not constitute a direct comparison with recorded ground motions. Due to the limited availability of strong-motion data in the Azores region, such

Figure 16. Inter-period correlation of normalized residual of SA with respect to empirical GMMs for bedrock condition.

Figure 17. Inter-period correlation of normalized residual of SA with respect to empirical GMMs for soil profile III condition.

a comparison is not feasible. However, the selected GMMs are based on recorded motions from diverse regions and site conditions and serve as a practical reference. It is worth noting that empirical GMMs may exhibit stronger inter-period correlations because real ground motion datasets capture systematic, physically coherent effects across periods, arising from diverse but internally consistent source, path, and site scenarios, that are not fully parameterized in the stochastic model. In contrast, the stochastic simulations assume more controlled and homogeneous conditions, with randomness introduced largely through uncorrelated stochastic components, which may result in lower ρ_ε values. Despite these differences, the overall inter-period correlation trends remain consistent, reinforcing the internal coherence of the simulation framework.

Stochastic simulations, which are considered suitable for modeling medium- to high-frequency ground motions, often underestimate the variability of recordings (Burks and Baker 2014). As a result, the standard deviation of ε values (σ_ε) is typically much smaller than one. Figure 18 illustrates ε (first row) and σ_ε values (second row) for the simulated bedrock and soil profile III datasets. The simulations on bedrock show varying levels of ε with respect to different GMMs, oscillating around zero. However, while the simulations on soil profile III hover slightly below zero at shorter periods (<0.5 s), they consistently yield lower ε values at longer periods. Moreover, the σ_ε values are approximately above 0.5 for both datasets with respect to most GMMs. The higher σ_ε values at shorter periods (<0.5 s), oscillating around one, are attributed to the amplification behavior of soil profile III, as noted earlier in Figure 14. It is noteworthy that the limited representation of site conditions, with only two cases of bedrock and soil profile III (V_{S30} of 340 m/s), leads to lower variability. This agrees with previous studies (Altindal and Askan 2023), which suggest that incorporating a broader range of input parameters could help achieve a better balance in variability.

Figures 19 and 20 show the mean value of ε of PGA (ε_{PGA}), along with one standard deviation, as a function of R_{JB} values. The ε_{PGA} values for the bedrock dataset generally fluctuate around zero with respect to BCKBSG17 and AC10, while for the soil profile III dataset, they fluctuate around zero with respect to ASB14, KWBC20, and AC10. The lower ε_{PGA} values for BJF1997 indicate a higher attenuation of the simulated PGA values with respect to this GMM. Nonetheless, the ε_{PGA} remains relatively stable across the range of R_{JB} values.

Figure 18. Normalized residual of SA (ϵ_{SA}) and its standard deviation ($\sigma_{\epsilon_{SA}}$) with respect to empirical GMMs for bedrock and soil profile III conditions.

Figure 19. Normalized residual of PGA (ϵ_{PGA}) against R_{JB} with respect to empirical GMMs for bedrock conditions.

Figure 20. Normalized residual of PGA (ϵ_{PGA}) against R_{JB} with respect to empirical GMMs for soil profile III conditions.

The validation framework applied in this study shows that the simulations in general align with the selected GMMs in terms of intensity levels, attenuation behavior, residual analysis, and inter-period correlation of spectral acceleration. Although the simulations were limited to two site conditions (bedrock and a soil profile III profile with a V_{S30} of 340 m/s), they provide valuable insights into the seismic behavior of the Azores region, laying the groundwork for future seismic hazard analyses. Empirical GMMs, derived from a broader range of data covering various regions, soil profiles, and seismic scenarios, capture a wider variability in ground motions. However, these models exhibit different intensity levels and attenuation behaviors, emphasizing the need for region-specific models tailored to the Azores' unique seismic characteristics. Therefore, future studies should address these limitations by considering a broader range of site conditions and amplification behaviors to better capture ground motion variability, thereby enhancing the reliability of seismic hazard assessments in the region. As highlighted by (Motazedian and Atkinson 2005), stochastic methodologies have struggled to accurately capture the coherent, long-period pulses that significantly influence ground motion characteristics in near-fault regions, particularly with respect to PGV and long period SA. Although the present simulations reproduced these features to a reasonable extent (accounting for less than 1% of the dataset), their limited occurrence suggests that incorporating additional parameter variability or epistemic uncertainty may be advisable if these features are of direct interest for seismic hazard analysis.

5. Conclusions

This study develops and validates a simulated ground motion dataset for the Azores Plateau, Portugal, addressing the scarcity of recorded accelerograms in the region, using a stochastic source-based approach, i.e., stochastic finite-fault modeling with a dynamic corner frequency concept after (Motazedian and Atkinson 2005). Previous studies by Karimzadeh, Mohammadi et al. (2023) and Ji

et al. (2025) generated synthetic ground motion records at rock sites, incorporating randomized input-model parameters to capture variability in seismic activity. This study captures aleatory variability through parameter randomization, but a formal epistemic uncertainty analysis was not performed and should be addressed in future work. Building upon these efforts, the present study extends the dataset to include soil-amplified records and establishes a comprehensive validation framework for both rock and soil simulations. The one-dimensional stochastic nonlinear site response analysis accounts for soil amplification effects of soil profile III ($V_{S30} = 340$ m/s) according to the Portuguese National Annex of Eurocode 8 (IPQ 2010). The dataset is then validated against empirical ground motion models (GMMs) and inter-period correlation analyses to ensure its accuracy in representing regional seismic hazard.

Key findings and insights from this study:

- The simulated dataset provides acceleration time series for earthquake magnitudes ranging from M_w 5.0 to 6.8, covering both bedrock and soil profile III ($V_{S30} = 340$ m/s), addressing the shortage of recorded accelerograms for the Azores Plateau in Portugal.
- The one-dimensional stochastic nonlinear site response analysis reveals notable soil amplification effects at short periods, with pronounced nonlinear behavior observed during stronger ground motions. Additionally, the soil conditions exhibit higher intensity levels compared to bedrock, reflecting amplification effects due to the soil profile.
- A small fraction ($\sim 0.65\%$) of simulated motions exhibit pulse-like characteristics, indicating the presence of near-fault effects. Refinements in long-period ground motion modeling are recommended if these features are of direct interest in seismic hazard analysis.
- The stochastic finite-fault simulation approach effectively captures expected attenuation trends of peak ground acceleration (PGA), peak ground velocity (PGV), and spectral acceleration ordinates at different periods in both bedrock and soil, ensuring a realistic seismic hazard representation. Spectral acceleration comparisons indicate that simulated motions follow expected trends with distance and magnitude, validating the dataset's ability to capture the geometric and anelastic attenuation of seismic waves. Additionally, the dataset accurately replicates the shift in peak spectral acceleration toward longer periods as magnitude increases, confirming its consistency with observed seismic behavior.
- The simulated dataset closely aligns with empirical GMMs, with intensity levels largely within one standard deviation of existing models, confirming its reliability for engineering applications.
- The simulated dataset effectively captures the inter-period correlation of spectral acceleration, though slightly higher correlation values are observed with respect to some empirical models among others, more so at higher periods than lower periods.
- Normalized residual analysis confirms that the simulations maintain stable intensity levels across different distances, with attenuation trends closely aligning with empirical GMMs in most cases. Additionally, residual analysis of spectral ordinates shows that simulated motions oscillate around zero relative to empirical models, with minor deviations attributed to differences in datasets and site representation.
- The simulated dataset shows slightly lower variability than empirical models, likely due to the limited range of site conditions considered in comparison to those models, which are restricted to bedrock and a soil profile III ($V_{S30} = 340$ m/s).
- Compared to recorded datasets, the stochastic method successfully captures medium- to high-frequency ground motions, making it a valuable tool for seismic hazard and risk assessments in Azores region with limited records.

Overall, this study presents an alternative, validated ground motion dataset for the Azores Plateau, significantly enhancing seismic hazard assessment capabilities in the region. The findings emphasize the crucial role of region-specific ground motion datasets in seismic hazard and risk analysis and demonstrate the effectiveness of stochastic simulations in regions with limited recorded data. While

the dataset serves as a valuable and reliable resource, its applicability in engineering structural assessment could be further improved by expanding the range of site conditions considered. Incorporating additional site classes (e.g. profiles II, IV, and V) in future simulations would also enable a more comprehensive assessment of site amplification variability and its influence on the dispersion of ground motion parameters across the Azores. Although the 1D stochastic nonlinear approach captures strain-dependent soil behavior, future studies should explore fully nonlinear time-domain analyses to further quantify modulus degradation and hysteretic damping effects for large magnitude scenarios. Future extensions of this work should incorporate two- and three-dimensional topographic and basin effects to better quantify localized amplification and long-period response variability across the volcanic terrains of the Azores. Additionally, refinements in long-period motion modeling and the integration of hybrid broadband simulation approaches would enhance the representation of near-fault effects. The EXSIM12 stochastic finite-fault model, while effective for mid- and high-frequency simulations, has limitations in reproducing near-fault and long-period features such as directivity pulses, due to its simplified kinematic rupture representation. These limitations can lead to an underrepresentation of long-period energy content and velocity pulses, which are particularly critical for PGV-sensitive structures and long-period engineering demands (e.g. tall buildings, bridges, and lifelines) located near fault ruptures. Therefore, caution is advised when interpreting long-period ground motions derived from EXSIM12 in near-fault conditions. Future developments should aim to integrate more physically realistic rupture models to enhance the reliability of near-fault ground motion predictions. Given the absence of a dedicated empirical GMM for the Azores region, future research should prioritize the development of a region-specific GMM, integrating both simulated and recorded data to further strengthen seismic hazard assessments and earthquake engineering applications.

Author Contributions

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Data Availability Statement

The ground motion simulation datasets for both bedrock and representative soil profiles, together with their accompanying flat-files containing metadata and spectral acceleration ordinates, are publicly available at <https://zenodo.org/records/16759850>. and <https://zenodo.org/records/16760903>.

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